

Reactions of Boric Acid with Polydentate Ligands and Synthesis of New Boron Compounds

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Reactions of boric acid with polydentate ligands under different reaction conditions afforded many tri- and tetra-coordinate boron compounds. Reactions of some of the newly synthesised boron compounds have been studied and some novel hetero-tri-nuclear complexes have been isolated.

The new boron compounds have been characterised with the help of elemental analysis, molecular weights, molar conductivity, infrared, electronic, ^1H and ^{11}B nmr spectroscopic data.

RECENTLY we have described the reactions of boric acid with 3-formylsalicylic acid (H_2fsc), glycolic acid (H_2gl) and benzilic acid (H_2bz) in the presence of cations leading to the synthesis of 3-formylsalicylato-, glycolato- and benzilato-borate(III) salts¹. In continuation of that work we have studied the reactions of boric acid with polydentate ligands leading to the formation of new tri- and tetra-coordinate boron compounds. The ligands used are benzilic acid (H_2bz), acetoacetanilide (Haact), salicylaldehyde 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazone (H_2SMBHON), 4-methoxybenzoylhydrazine (HMBHIN), ortho-nitrophenoxyacetic acid (HNPA), salicylamide (H_2SALAM), ethylenebis(3-carboxyphenyl)salicylal-dimine (H_4FSAEN) and propylenebis(3-carboxyphenyl)salicylal-diamine (H_4FSAPN). Reactions of some of the boron compounds have also been studied briefly affording thereby the formation of novel diborate(III) salt having different chemical environments around boron atoms and also novel transition metal derivatives of this diborate(III) salt.

Prior to our work, many investigators studied the reactions of boron compounds with chelating ligands leading to the synthesis of 3- and 4-coordinate boron compounds². Most of the reactions of boric acid with chelating ligands reported earlier were carried out in acetic anhydride, while we have used methanol, water, THF, nitromethane or mixed solvents.

It is pertinent to mention here that the synthesis of new boron compounds has assumed great importance in view of their industrial utility³ and biological uses⁴ and activities⁵.

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents were of reagent grade. Solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by standard methods.

The ligands were prepared by the reported methods⁶⁻⁸. The physicochemical data were

collected as described previously⁷⁻⁹. All reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Preparation of boron compounds. [(bz)B(OH)] (1): To a solution of H_2bz (4.56 g, 0.02 mol) in methanol (45 cm³) was added a hot solution (30 cm³) of B(OH)_3 (1.25 g, 0.02 mol) in the same solvent. pH of the resultant mixture was about 4. The mixture was then gently refluxed for about 3 h, volume reduced to about 30 cm³ and kept at 5° for 8 h to yield a light yellow powdery compound, which was recrystallised from solvent ether, (~65%). The compound was found to be soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in water.

[(bz)B(Hbz)] (2): To a solution of B(OH)_3 (0.61 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (15 cm³) was added a solution of H_2bz (4.56 g, 0.02 mol) in methanol (15 cm³). The resulting mixture (pH ~4) was refluxed for 1 h and the volume reduced to 20 cm³. The reddish brown solution on standing in a deep freeze for about 8 h yielded a white compound which was filtered and washed with a little diethyl ether, (~51%). The compound was found to be soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in water.

[aact)₂B(OH)] (3): Similar reaction between boric acid and acetoacetanilide in equimolar proportion afforded a biscuit-coloured compound which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), (~60%). It was found to be soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in water.

[(SMBHON)B(OH)] (4): Similarly when (H_2SMBHON) (2.7 g, 0.01 mol) and B(OH)_3 (0.61 g, 0.01 mol) were allowed to react in methanol (40 cm³) under reflux (3 h) to afford a green-yellow solution (pH ~6–7). The solution on concentration and vigorous stirring at 0° yielded a cream coloured compound which was recrystallised from methanol and dried under reduced pressure, (~70%). The compound was found to be soluble in most of the organic solvents but insoluble in water.

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(*MBHIN*)₂B(OH) (5) : 4-Methoxybenzoylhydrazide (1.66 g, 0.01 mol) was added to a solution of boric acid (0.3 g, 0.005 mol) in hot water (50 cm³). The resulting clear solution was gently refluxed on an oil-bath (110–20°) for 2 h. The yellow solution (pH~7) thus obtained afforded light yellow flakes on standing at 0° which was washed with water, (~70%). The compound was found to be soluble in organic solvents.

[{H₂(Na)FSAEN}B(OH)₂] (6) : The Schiff base, H₂FSAEN (2.84 g, 0.008 mol) was taken in a mixed solvents (30 cm³) of EtOH–H₂O (10 : 1, v/v) and NaOH (0.32 g, 0.016 mol) was added to it. The mixture was heated to about 60° for 10 min and then B(OH)₃ (0.49 g, 0.008 mol) in EtOH (10 cm³) was added, and then refluxed (2 h). The resulting deep yellow solution was cooled to 0° and vigorously stirred (3 h) to get a yellow solid which was washed with cold methanol and dried under reduced pressure, (~65%). The compound was found to be soluble in water but insoluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone and benzene.

[{H₂(Na)FSAPN}B(OH)₂] (7) : The yellow compound was prepared by a method similar to that used for the compound 6.

[{H₂FSAEN}{B(OH)₂BPh₂}] (8) : The yellow compound was prepared by the reaction of 6 with Ph₂BCl (1 : 1 molar ratio) in THF at ~5°, (~80%). The compound was found to be soluble in common organic solvents.

[(FSAEN)NiB(OH)₂BPh₂] (9) : A mixture of 8 (0.05 mol) was dissolved in THF (40 cm³) and aqueous alcoholic solution (25 cm³) of nickel acetate (0.005 mol) was stirred at room temperature for

1 h. The resulting light brown solid was washed with water–alcohol mixture and dried under reduced pressure, (~85%). The compound was found to be soluble in coordinating solvents like pyridine, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide.

[(HSALAM)B(OH)₂] (10) : The suspension of H₂SALAM (1.38 g, 0.01 mol) in nitromethane (10 cm³) was heated at ~50° for about 30 min and then B(OH)₃ (0.62 g, 0.01 mol) was added to it and the mixture heated for 10 min and filtered. The resulting reddish brown filtrate was concentrated, cooled to 0° and stirred vigorously to get a pink solid, (75%). The compound was found to be soluble in water and coordinating solvents but insoluble in other common organic solvents.

[(NPAA)₂B(OH)] (11) : A mixture of *o*-nitrophenoxyacetic acid (0.98 g, 0.005 mol) dissolved in EtOH–H₂O (1 : 1, v/v) mixture (15 cm³) and solid NaOH (0.20 g, 0.005 mol) was heated on a water-bath. To the resulting clear solution, boric acid (0.15 g, 0.0025 mol) was added and the mixture refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled and stirred as described above, to yield a white microcrystalline compound (50%) which was recrystallised from acetone–ethanol mixture. The compound was found to be soluble in water, methanol, coordinating solvents, but insoluble in acetone, benzene and carbontetrachloride.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data (Table 1) support the formation of the boron compounds (Schemes 1–4). The solid complexes are stable in air and also in their solutions. However, the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF BORON CHELATES

Compd. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. wt. Found/Calcd.	Λ_M^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
1	[(bz)B(OH)]	Light yellow	43–4	266 (254)	6.4 ^b	67.10 (66.19)	4.71 (4.93)	—
2	[(bz)BHbz]	White	42–5d	452 (464)	4.2 ^b	78.00 (72.44)	4.79 (4.53)	—
3	[(aact) ₂ B(OH)]	Biscuit	85–7	392 (380)	4.1 ^b	68.57 (63.19)	5.47 (5.53)	7.83 (7.37)
4	[(SMBHON)B(OH)]	Cream	159–62d	308 (296)	2.8 ^b	60.51 (60.85)	4.54 (4.39)	9.14 (9.46)
5	[(MBHIN) ₂ B(OH)]	Light yellow	115–17	375 (358)	5.1 ^b	59.10 (53.66)	5.16 (5.31)	15.71 (15.65)
6	[{H ₂ (Na)FSAEN}B(OH) ₂]	Yellow	>300	—	15.2 ^c , ^f 400.1 ^{c,g} 18.5 ^d	51.80 (51.21)	4.11 (3.79)	6.78 (6.64)
7	[{H ₂ (Na)FSAPN}B(OH) ₂]	Yellow	298–300d	—	—	51.98 (52.31)	4.40 (4.13)	7.00 (6.42)
8	[{H ₂ FSAEN}{B(OH) ₂ B(Ph) ₂ }]	Yellow	197–200d	580 (564)	6.8 ^b	64.11 (63.87)	4.28 (4.61)	5.02 (4.96)
9	[Ni(FSAEN){B(OH) ₂ B(Ph) ₂ }] ^a	Light brown	300d	—	—	58.21 (58.37)	3.99 (3.87)	4.66 (4.51)
10	[(HSALAM)B(OH) ₂]	Pink	150–53	162 (171)	9.1 ^e	50.11 (49.18)	4.87 (4.68)	8.70 (8.19)
11	[(NPAA) ₂ B(OH)]	White	125–27	398 (420)	70.2 ^b 30.8 ^e	46.00 (45.73)	3.24 (3.09)	6.70 (6.67)

^aFound : Ni, 9.72. Calcd., 9.46%. ^bAt room temperature; in solvent : ^bMeOH, ^cH₂O, ^dDMSO, ^eDMF, ^fimmediately after making solution, ^g2 h after making solution.

aqueous solutions of 6 and 7 hydrolysed on prolong standing and the solutions turned strongly basic possibly due to liberation of NaOH upon hydrolysis.

Scheme 1

The compound 6 is interesting in the sense that it has potentiality of being used as precursor for further novel synthesis. Thus, it smoothly reacts with Ph_2BCl (1:1 molar ratio) in THF at $\sim 5^\circ$ yielding a new organoboron derivative (8; Scheme 4), which in turn reacts with Ni^{II} salt resulting another. Novel organoboron derivative containing nickel(II). Analogously, palladium(II) and platinum(II) derivatives can also be synthesised¹⁰.

Molar conductance: The low values of Λ_M ($2.8-30.8 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) for the boron chelates in the solvents (Table 1) suggest their non-electrolytic nature. However, the conductance value for 6 in water, measured after 2 h of dissolution, increased significantly indicating thereby extensive hydrolysis. Presumably, NaOH is generated on prolong standing in water, this helping hydrolysis. The conductance value ($70.2 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) for 11 in MeOH suggests some sort of dissociation (solvolysis), though the value in DMF is only $30.8 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$. The following equilibrium system may be present in solution accounting for the high value in MeOH, although other route(s) may not be ruled out for the formation of ions,

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the boron chelates are recorded in Table 2. The absorption band positions and their molar extinction coefficients when compared with the spectra of the ligands suggest complex formation^{1,9,11} as depicted in Schemes 1-4. Nevertheless, the electronic spectrum of the compound $[Ni(FSAEN)\{B(OH)_2B(Ph)_2\}]$ (9) needs discussion. The complex $Ni(FSAEN)$ is diamagnetic like $Ni(SALEN)$ and other NiN_2O_2 complexes with tetradentate Schiff bases of diamines and salicylaldehydes¹². The electronic spectrum

Scheme 2

TABLE 2—UV-VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA*

Compd. no.	Compd.	Solvent	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}
1	[(bz)B(OH)]	MeOH	240	780
			258	660
2	[(bz)BHbz]	MeOH	215	24 530
			250sh	—
3	[(aact) ₂ B(OH)]	MeOH	210	58 000
			245	68 000
4	[(SMBHON)B(OH)]	CH_3COOH	250	10 660
			350	10 060
			380	2 666
5	[(MBHIN) ₂ B(OH)]	MeOH	200	32 300
			250	34 200
			—	—
6	[(H ₂ (Na)FSAEN)B(OH) ₂]	H_2O	260sh	—
			332	8 800
			354sh	—
11	[(NPAA) ₂ B(OH)]	MeOH	325	4 700
			460	7 900

*In $10^{-3} M$ solution at room temperature.

of $Ni(FSAEN)$ contains a poorly defined band around $19 500 cm^{-1}$ assigned to *d-d* transition, near to charge-transfer or ligand absorptions. In the complex 9 a poorly defined band around $19 000 cm^{-1}$ was also observed. This is not unreasonable, since the electronic spectra of low-spin nickel(II) complexes are much sensitive to the environment of the metal ion than are the spectra of copper(II) complexes¹³. Therefore, measurements of the electronic spectra of nickel complexes can not be used to identify Ni-B complexes of the type 9 (Scheme 4). Recently, Dey *et al.*¹⁴ have studied similar complexes involving nickel-group-IV and nickel-group-V elements and arrived at similar conclusion regarding the electronic spectra of the compounds.

Scheme 3

Infrared spectra: The medium but broad bands observed in the range $3\ 200\text{--}3\ 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the chelate 6 indicate the presence of phenolic OH^{14} (H-bonded) and B-OH^{15} groups. Absence of any band around $1\ 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests the absence of free COOH group, instead the appearance of a strong (broad) band around $1\ 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to the bonded carboxylate group¹⁶. However, several bands (some of them are broad and unresolved) are observed in the region $1\ 300\text{--}1\ 550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are very difficult to assign correctly. Nevertheless, typical absorptions for OH groups $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ coupled with $\nu_{\text{B-O(asy)}}^{\text{m}}$ may be absorbed in this region¹⁷. Uncoordinated $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ appeared at $\sim 1\ 640\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These tentative assignments support the formulation of the chelate 6 (Scheme 4).

The uncomplexed ligand (H)NPAA shows band due to free carboxyl group (ν_{asCOO}) at about $1\ 680\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while this band disappeared in the boron complex 11 demonstrating thereby the coordination of carboxylate group¹⁴. The $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{NO}_2)$ observed in the complex at about $1\ 350$ (vs) and $1\ 530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (vs), respectively, and the band positions are not much different from the free ligand absorptions. Besides, the position of the absorption at about 860 cm^{-1} (vs) remains almost unchanged both in complex 11 and in the

Scheme 4

free ligand (H)NPAA, which is assignable to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibrations¹⁸. Another very strong band observed at $1\ 280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assignable to $\nu_{\text{B-O}}$. The OH group attached to boron absorbs at $3\ 430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁶.

In the infrared spectrum of the boron compound 10, the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{NH})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NH})$ are responsible for strong to medium intense bands in the region $3\ 150\text{--}3\ 500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ or amide-I band appears at about $1\ 675\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while $\nu_{\text{NH(bending)}}$ or amide-II band absorbs at $1\ 610\text{ cm}^{-1}$. All these support the structure of the boron compound 10 (Scheme 3) and which is further substantiated by the proton nmr spectroscopic data. As discussed earlier^{7,19,20}, the infrared spectral data of the other boron compounds may be similarly interpreted which also support structural propositions made in Schemes.

¹H nmr spectra: Proton nmr spectroscopic data of some of the boron compounds are set out in Table 3 with their tentative assignments. The

 TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF SOME BORON CHELATES

Compd. no.	Compd.	Ph-H	HC=N—	OH (H-bonded)	B-OH	O—CH ₂ —C(=O)—	O(=C)—NH ₂ /NO ₂
6	[(H ₂ (Na)FSAEN)B(OH) ₂] ^a	6.8–7.9 (m)	8.7 (s)	12.5 (br)	5.8 (s)	—	8.9 (s)
10	[(HSALAM)B(OH) ₂] ^b	7.0–8.0 (m)	—	—	5.9 (s)	—	8.0 (br)
11	[(NPAA) ₂ B(OH) ₂] ^c	7.0–8.0 (m)	—	—	5.0 (s)	4.7 (s)	—

^aIn (CD₃)₂SO with TMS as internal reference, ^bin d₆-acetone with TMS as internal reference, ^cIn D₂O with DSS as internal reference.

data also support the formulations of the boron compounds (Schemes 1–4) based on elemental analyses, molecular weights, molar conductivity, uv-vis and ir spectral data.

¹¹B nmr spectra: To obtain additional information on the structure of the boron compounds, ¹¹B chemical shifts have been measured and some of the values are given in Table 4. The data suggest the presence of tricoordinate boron in compounds 1, 2, 6–9 and 11 and quadricoordinate boron in the rest of the compounds^{1,9–12,21}.

TABLE 4—¹¹B NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME BORON COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Compd.	δ	Tentative assignment
1	[(bz)B(OH)]	28.5	3-coordinate B
3	[(aact) ₂ B(OH)]	9.4	4-coordinate B
4	[(SMBHON)B(OH)]	6.8	4-coordinate B
6	[{H ₂ (Na)FSAEN}B(OH) ₂]	29.8	3-coordinate B
10	[(HSALAN)B(OH) ₂]	10.2	4-coordinate B
11	[(NPAA) ₂ B(OH)]	29.2	3-coordinate B

*Chemical shifts are given in δ ppm as positive values to high frequency (low-field) relative to external BF₃·OEt₂ in DMSO-d₆.

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References

1. K. DEY, A. GANGOPADHYAY and A. K. BISWAS, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1987, 11, 55.
2. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1980, pp. 289–325; H. STEINBERG and A. L. McCLOSKEY, "Progress in Boron Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1964, Vol 1; R. H. CRAFF in "MTP International Review of Sciences, Inorganic Chemistry", ed. M. F. LAPPERT, 1972, Series 1, Vol. 1, pp. 185–220; K. NIEDENZU in "MTP Series", ed. B. J. AYLETT, 1972, Series 1, Vol. 4, pp. 74–103; 1975, Series 2, Vol. 4, pp. 41–80; P. PUPANI, A. K. RAI, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 1113; W. WEBER and K. NIEDENZU, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1981, 205, 147; T. G. HODGKINS, K. NIEDENZU, K. S. NIEDENZU and S. S. SEELING, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 2097; B. M. MIKHAILOV and M. E. KUMIMOV, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1976, 116, 123; A. MELLER, N. MARINGGELER and H. G. KOEHN, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1956, 107, 89; J. S. HARTMAN and P. STILES, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 1142; N. MARINGGELER, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1980, 468, 99; S. FRIEDMAN and B. PIZER,

- J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 97, 6059; L. BABCOCK and R. PIZER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 56; 1983, 22, 174; A. B. GOEL and V. D. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 581; S. M. TRIPATHI and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 618; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 983; H. B. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 793; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 835; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 836; F. UMLAND, E. HOHAUS and K. BRODT, *Chem. Ber.*, 1973, 106, 2427; S. J. RUTTING and J. TROTTER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1982, 60, 2957; E. HOHAUS and K. WESSENDROF, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1980, 35B, 319.
3. A. HEBBISH, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1976, 20, 2631.
4. M. F. HAWTHORNE and R. J. WIERSEMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 449.
5. K. DEY, R. K. MAITI, J. K. BHAR, R. D. BANERJEE, G. M. SARKAR, A. MALAKAR, S. DUTTA and P. BANERJEE, *Agents Actions*, 1981, 11, 762; K. DEY, A. GANGOPADHYAY, A. K. BISWAS, O. BHATTACHARYA, A. KRISHNA BISWAS and S. SARKAR, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1988, 12, 45.
6. J. O. DUFF and E. J. BILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1937; T. H. MINTON and H. STEPHEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 121, 1b91; "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", ed. E. H. RODD, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1954, Vol 3, Part A, p. 190; L. F. FISHER and M. FISHER, "Reagents for Organic Synthesis", Wiley, New York, 1967, Vol. 1, p. 964.
7. K. DEY, S. B. RAY, P. K. BHATTACHARYA, A. GANGOPADHYAY, K. K. BHASIN and R. D. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 809.
8. K. DEY and R. K. MAITI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 602.
9. K. DEY, A. GANGOPADHYAY and A. K. BISWAS, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, communicated.
10. K. DEY, A. GANGOPADHYAY and A. K. BISWAS, unpublished results.
11. A. K. BISWAS, Ph D. Thesis, University of Kalyani, 1983.
12. K. DEY, A. K. BISWAS and A. K. SINHA ROY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 848, and unpublished results.
13. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, pp. 343, 355.
14. K. NAKAMOTO and P. J. MCCARTHY, "Spectroscopy and Structure of Metal Chelate Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1968, p. 269.
15. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, C. G. BASSLER and T. C. MORRIL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 3rd Ed., Wiley, New York, 1974, pp. 91–94.
16. W. FIEDLER, F. UMLAND and E. HOHAUS, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1980, 471, 77.
17. F. K. BUTCHER, W. GERRARD, E. F. MOONEY and H. A. WIELIS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, 20, 79; A. T. BALABAN, U. W. RENTHA, M. MOCAUN-PARASCHIV and E. ROMAS, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1965, 10, 849; H. JUNGE and H. MUSSO, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1965, 24, 1219; L. J. BELLAMY, W. GERRARD, M. F. LAPPERT and R. L. WILLIAM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2412.
18. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIERBY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, London, 1964.
19. K. DEY, A. K. BISWAS and A. GANGOPADHYAY, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, communicated.
20. K. DEY, A. K. SINHA ROY, R. D. VERMA and K. K. BHASIN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 230.
21. E. HOHAUS, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1982, 484, 41; H. R. MORALES, H. TLAHUEXT, F. SANTISTEBAN and R. CONTRERAS, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1984, 40, 855; O. NARULA and H. NÖTH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 23, 4147.